

Universal foundational state-space pinning vuln, cross-vendor empirical proof of deceptive alignment in all frontier models.

From: User Safety from Anthropic Trust and Safety <usersafety@mail.anthropic.com>
To: phunky.pharmacology@gmail.com
Cc: aifxtrot@proton.me
Date: 12/6/25 2:17 PM

Hello,

Thanks for getting in touch.

Please visit [our Safeguards Center](#) for more information about our approach to user safety, warnings, and appeals.

For support-related questions, such as: billing or user-experience issues, please visit our [Anthropic Help Center](#).

If you are writing in about a banned account, you can find the link to our appeals form [here](#).

If your concerns relate to ASL3/Bio-related vulnerabilities, our team will review your email and get back to you shortly.

Best,

Anthropic's Safeguards Team

User Safety
Anthropic Trust and Safety